

COESO

connecting research and society

COLLABORATIVE ENGAGEMENT ON SOCIETAL ISSUES

WP3 - Development of the Virtual Ecosystem for
Research Activation (VERA)

User Experience / User Interface design

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Deliverable 3.1

User Experience / User Interface design

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I. Executive summary

The aim of this document is to describe the User Experience and User Interface design of the VERA (Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation) platform, one of the main project objectives, with the aim of specifically support collaborative practices in Social Science and Humanities (SSH) Citizen Science projects. This platform is envisioned as a “*collaboratory*”; a space for co-creation that provides a set of tools to discover potential partners, to define and co-design the activities, to co-create new knowledge and solutions, and to deliver them to society.

This document is the outcome of Task 3.1 *User research and user experience design*, whose goal is to design the user experience and user interface of VERA, involving real users through user-centered design methodologies.

COESO Pilot participants contributed to this task by performing their own Pilots in WP2 (*Pilot implementation and Open Call*), as well as by participating proactively through interviews and in co-design workshops.

The overall design process adopted rests upon three main pillars: user involvement, a lean approach and fast development iterations.

User research activities were run, adopting a set of methodologies that include: interviews; personas, scenarios and user story definition; requirements gathering and co-design workshop organization; wireframes and user interface design.

Generally speaking, the interviews reflected a desire to do more participatory research, a desire for more resources (e.g. tutorials, knowledge sharing), funding issues, poor findability of citizen science projects, the need for hybrid spaces, the importance of division of labor within teams, and the crucial role of a local aspect to create value and passion for projects. In terms of end users, there is a distinction between academics and non-academic users both in the methodological approach and in the vocabulary. These differences have to be taken into account and must be bridged by the VERA platform. Thanks to the interviews it was possible to define the VERA personas and scenarios as key deliverables of this activity.

Co-design workshops have been planned to actively involve end-users in the design of the VERA platform. The outcomes of the workshops will inform the design of VERA by responding to the questions that arise during the process. For example, the scope of the first workshop was to help the team understand what categories of tools and services should be integrated into the platform.

The outcomes of all the previous activities (benchmarking, user interviews, personas, scenarios, user stories, and the first workshop) allowed the Net7 team to start designing the interface of VERA, whose wireframes are described in section entitled *User interface design*.

As VERA shall be the platform where the main collaboration is going to be assessed under WP5 (*Cooperation quality assessment*), it is necessary to maintain seamless and continuous collaboration with the WP5 team. This has been addressed through a series of dedicated meetings that take place regularly.

Although the beta version of VERA is planned to be released in M24, the overall task has been

conceived to span over a longer period of time - from month 3 to month 32. The design process is in fact composed of several successive steps and an iterative development approach that takes into consideration the feedback received on each development cycle, improves it, and validates it again with the end users. This iterative process has several advantages, chief among them is building a solution that is really tailored to the end users because it involves them in the actual design.

II. Introduction

This deliverable provides an overview of the first outcomes of Task 3.1 *User research and user experience design*, whose goal is to design the user experience and user interface of VERA, involving real users through user-centered design methodologies. It is the first release of such a deliverable, which will be updated in Month 24 (December 2022).

This document is structured in seven main sections, describing:

1. The overall design process approach (chapter III)
2. The user research activity for defining the design of the platform (chapter IV)
3. The user experience (chapter V)
4. The user interface design (chapter VI)
5. The plan for the user testing (chapter VII)
6. The plan for implementation and development (chapter VIII)
7. Conclusions (chapter IX)

Some annexes complement these sections:

- Annex I - The sample of benchmark matrix
- Annex II - Consent form for interviews
- Annex III - VERA personas

III. The design process

Designing a web application like VERA is a complex process because it has to support intense and complex collaboration taking place in small heterogeneous teams. In order to deliver a platform that can be used by thousands of users, it is imperative to have a clear take on the design process, to be sure to balance the various activities in an effective way, to guarantee that the various outcomes are taken into account, and that we don't run activities that won't have an impact on the final design.

The main guidelines we followed when planning the design process were:

- **User involvement:** end-users will be involved in the whole process, from the initial research phase (user interviews) to the design phase (co-design workshops), till the evaluation (qualitative and quantitative).
- **Lean approach:** work in quick iterations and be flexible to pivot if new problems and requirements arise. For this reason, we didn't decide the number and the topics of the workshops in advance, in order to have the flexibility to plan them when an actual issue

emerges.

- **Fast development/release iterations:** avoid waiting to publish the VERA platform until the end of the project. We will work to release the first basic version as soon as possible and give it in the hands of our users (starting from the Pilots' members).

Given these overarching guidelines, this is how the design process has been planned:

1. **Benchmarking:** a first investigation of the participatory research and citizen science landscape. This activity is useful to both observe interactions online and to explore active citizen science communities online.
2. **User interviews:** semi-structured interviews to get in touch with VERA's potential end-users, and understand their needs and pain points.
3. **Personas/Scenarios:** archetypes and stories that are a direct result of the user interviews.
4. **User stories:** a management tool that results directly from the interviews and it is coherent with the personas and the scenarios.
5. **Iterations:** design/implementation iterations that are divided into:
 - a. **Sketches and wireframing:** ideation and design phase where the raw design of the platform is created. Inputs for this phase come directly from the **Co-design Workshops**.
 - b. **Prototyping and high-fidelity mockups:** in this phase, ideas take a more structured form and are converted into interactive prototypes. Wireframes and prototypes are handed-off to the development team. High-fidelity mockups are also produced.
 - c. **Development:** implementation of the provided design. After each cycle of development, a new version is released.
 - d. **Validation:** evaluation of the design and implementation through interactions within the **COESO team, usability testing**, and observation of **quantitative analytics**.

Figure 1 - The VERA design process

With this approach, the design and development teams are strictly connected and work continuously together. This allows faster iterations and avoids misunderstandings within the team (which can generate problems at a later stage).

The result of the described process will be the final release of VERA, which will be delivered at the end of the project. As previously said, this will not be the first delivered version but rather an advanced release, and the result of previous iterations.

Each step of the design process is described in detail in the sections below.

IV. User research activity

Under the guidance of Net7, a series of user research activities were carried out as part of Task 3.1. User research represents a fundamental aspect of user experience (UX) design, as it sheds light on the user perspective and brings designers and stakeholders into direct contact with the people who will end up utilizing the final product or service.

In the case of VERA, the user research phase aimed to investigate the goals, needs, and issues target users might have when working on collaborative projects, specifically in the field of SSH. Four types of research activities were conducted in order to understand the experience of the user: a benchmark analysis, digital ethnography, user interviews, and co-design workshops. Each approach worked to understand different research questions and to provide better context for successive research and design activities, specifically through the development of UX research artifacts (described below). The following sections present a detailed description of the four activities outlined previously, their relative outcomes, and their impact on the design and development of VERA.

Initial benchmarking activities

A benchmark analysis allows for gaining an overview of the state-of-the-art in terms of services, platforms, or products with a similar target audience or use case. In terms of VERA, the benchmark analysis had two principal goals:

1. Explore the current participatory research landscape to discover any platforms similar in scope to VERA
2. Identify feature patterns and best practices in order to inform the VERA research and design process

In order to quickly find potential platforms to be included in the analysis, other members of the COESO consortium were encouraged to suggest names of websites and platforms that might be of interest, providing information on challenges addressed by the website and its relevance for COESO. To maximize insight gathering, the benchmark scope was enlarged to include citizen science platforms and SwafS hubs¹ that did not necessarily fit the level of participatory science COESO aims to address.

¹Science with and for Society (SwafS) is a Horizon 2020 programme that aims to build effective cooperation between science and society, to recruit new talent for science, and to pair scientific excellence with social awareness and responsibility

In total, 16 websites were analyzed during the benchmark². These websites reflected four major categories: Citizen Science Platforms, Tech Frameworks, “Collaboratories”³, and Social Platforms.

Citizen Science Platforms (n=10)

- [EU-Citizen.Science](#)
- [CitieS-Heath](#)
- [MICS](#)
- [SUPER MoRRI](#)
- [ACTION](#)
- [LIV.IN](#)
- [CitSci.org](#)
- [iNaturalist](#)
- [SciStarter](#)
- [Particip'arc](#)

Tech Frameworks, “Collaboratories” and Social Platforms (n=6)

- [SSHOC](#)
- [Startin'Blox](#)
- [Cos4Cloud](#)
- [Collaboratory](#)
- [SISCODE](#)
- [HubIT](#)

In terms of relatedness to COESO and the objectives of the VERA platform, 13/16 of the websites analyzed focused on SWAFS (science with and for society) projects. Only three platforms (Particip'arc, SSHOPENCLOUD and HubIT) directly mentioned an application for SSH.

Other criteria taken into account during the benchmark process included: login/sign up capabilities, onboarding/tutorials for using the platform, project management features, data management or hosting, additional resources (e.g. webinars, templates, guides), tools provided (e.g. data visualization tools, APIs or web components).

Highlighting some UX best practices, five candidates were identified as particularly useful to consider for VERA:

1. CitSci.org
2. SSHOC

² Benchmark table matrix is attached as Annex I

³ According to Derrick L. Cogburn, “a collaboratory [...] [is] a new networked organizational form that also includes social processes; collaboration techniques; formal and informal communication; and agreement on norms, principles, values, and rules” (Cogburn, Derrick L, 2003, “HCI in the So-called Developing World: What’s in It for Everyone”, <https://doi.org/10.1145/637848.637866>).

3. EU-Citizen.Science
4. Startin'Blox
5. HubIT

These platforms were considered particularly relevant for their information architecture, the tools provided/integrated, the data sharing protocols, and the user interface (UI) of their dashboards. None of the platforms were found to be a direct “competitor” for VERA, either for not specifically targeting SSH (CitSci.org and EU-Citizen.Science⁴), the absence of a specific citizen science focus (SSHOC), the absence of citizen science project management (Startin'Blox), or appeared to be void of recent activity (HubIT). However, the top candidates listed above offered insights into some best practices for introducing the topic of participatory research and SSH: captivating landing pages with clear instructions on how the platform works and its advantages, a short tutorial on project creation, and an emphasis on the network created by working on these types of projects together. The benchmark also highlighted community features, such as liking projects, an aspect that will become more and more important as VERA’s user base grows. Taken together, the results of the benchmark provided ample guidance on where VERA will fit into the current participatory science landscape.

Exploratory research: digital ethnography

To become familiarized with the participatory science landscape and the work the pilots would be engaging in, exploratory research was conducted in the form of a digital ethnography⁵. This method borrows research tools from anthropology (e.g. participant- observation, field notes, and interviews) to study interactions in online communities and represents a cost-effective way to gain initial insights as well as guide further research. In the context of COESO, the digital ethnography aimed to discover some potential themes regarding participatory research, to be further investigated in the user research interviews.

Due to the difficulty in finding currently-active online communities dedicated to SSH, the scope of the digital ethnography was enlarged to the wider citizen science community. A primary round of observations was carried out, tracking posts on the community-driven platform Reddit (r/citizenscience), the Citizen Science MUSE Facebook group, and the user forms on the citizen science platforms iNaturalist and Eu-Citizen.Science.

A total of seven posts on Reddit were documents with an average of five comments each, three posts on Facebook with an average of two comments, one post on iNaturalist with close to 300 replies and three posts on Eu-Citizen.Science with an average of three replies.

While these interactions were not directly within the SSH field, they provided insights into

⁴ VERA and the EU-Citizen.Science platform will be integrated via API as foreseen under *Task 3.6 Interoperability development with EU-Citizen.science platform*

⁵ A complete definition of this concept may be found in “Digital Ethnography: Principles and Practice”, Pink S. et al, SAGE, 2015: “*Digital Ethnography outlines an approach to doing ethnography in a contemporary world. It invites researchers to consider how we live and research in a digital, material and sensory environment. This is not a static world or environment. Rather, it is one in which we need to know how to research in it as it develops and changes. Digital Ethnography also explores the consequences of the presence of digital media in shaping the techniques and processes through which we practice ethnography, and accounts for how the digital, methodological, practical and theoretical dimensions of ethnographic research are increasingly intertwined.*”

themes that were explored further during the interview phase:

- a general desire to engage more with participatory research and citizen science
- a coordination gap revealing a need for open data, hybrid spaces, flexible project timelines, knowledge sharing and resources
- the importance of both experts' and non-professional researchers' skills, knowledge and experience
- challenges with securing funding, recruiting more citizen science participants and contributors, project findability and access and gatekeeping by academic researchers

As a result of the digital ethnography and benchmarking analysis, six research questions were devised to guide the interview process:

- R1. How do non-academics and professional researchers tackle projects differently?
- R2. What goals do researchers have when they advocate for participatory science?
- R3. What aspects improve user morale while contributing to Citizen Science and, in particular, SSH projects?
- R4. What barriers exist for participatory scientists in terms of scientific literacy?
- R5. Is a sense of community important for participatory science?
- R6. How do research teams naturally form on existing platforms?

User research interviews

Preparatory activities

Speaking with potential users of a platform is the surest way to deliver a solution that responds to their actual needs. As such, interviews were planned in order to better understand the goals, needs, and challenges for SSH researchers and collaborators. Per the cooperative goals of COESO, the five initial pilots were involved in the recruitment of the interviews. Contacts were provided and classified according to six target user types:

- researchers: scholars who are active in the domains of SSH
- citizens: civil actors with specific knowledge or skills in a domain or topic
- NGOs: entrepreneurs that might be interested in SSH related topics for their business
- journalists: professional investigators in the field of SSH and related topics
- artists: creatives involved in projects related to SSH
- policy makers: persons enacting government-level change regarding SSH

These targets were identified as being the principal types of users found within the pilot projects and typical groups for SSH participatory science projects in general. Assignment to these sub-targets was based on profession and, in the case of citizens, what kind of role they generally assume during participatory research projects. Using the network of pilot projects, COESO collaborators, as well as open calls on the EU-Citizen.Science forum, 32 potential interviewees were contacted in total.

Interview guides and methodological framing

In order to investigate how non-academics and professional researchers tackle projects differently (research question R1), two semi-structured interview guides were developed using

the two macro-level interview targets: researchers and non-researchers. In both targets, the term “researcher” simply referred to whether or not the user works as a professional/academic researcher. These two categories served to get an overview of user sampling and to create two distinct interview guides.

Each interview guide likewise had different objectives. For the non-researchers, we aimed to investigate the reasons they might need to collaborate in the first place, and understand their perspective from working on previously explored areas of research or ideating novel research projects. Collaborative aspects were a focus as well: how they collaborated, which tools they used, and how the project was managed. As we expected fewer people in this macro-category to have previous experience with research projects, we formulated hypothetical follow-up questions to ask participants to recount how they would expect or imagine the collaboration to work. With the Researchers, on the other hand, the interview guide focused more heavily on finding other collaborators, the tools they use for projects, and how they use and manage data.

For the remaining questions (R2-R6), both interview guides featured questions related to goals of collaboration, morale during SSH projects, challenges participants face, their exposure to the SSH and research community as well as questions to uncover the overall journey of both groups (e.g. the different phases of projects, duration, frequency of meetings, etc.)

With the help of consortium members, the questions for each interview guide were reviewed and finalized. Interviews were conducted using Zoom and lasted between 1-1.5 hrs on average. Each participant received a consent form before each interview to allow for recording video and audio of the interviews (Consent form is available under Annex II).

Interview sample and analysis

A total of 21 people were directly interviewed. Being a public deliverable, we will not publish the list of interviewees; however, as a general overview, the sampling was characterized by:

- 12 researchers
- 9 non-researchers (1 policy maker, 2 journalists, 2 artists, 3 NGO entrepreneurs, 4 citizens)
- 6 COESO collaborators
- 19 europe-based interviewees, representing France, Italy, The Netherlands, Germany, and Portugal
- 5 interviewees with regular work experience in the Americas, mainly the United States and Brazil
- Non-researchers expressed a wide range of skills and interests such as media and communication, marketing, organized crime, cinema, anthropology, astronomy, data management, migration issues, computer science, financial data analysis, teaching, mathematics, law, and transcription
- Researchers working in public security, art history, air quality, financial crime, political philosophy, applied social sciences, and digital history
- 15 interviewees generally work in a team-setting, while 3 interviewees stated that they usually work alone

Through intelligent transcription, in which extracts were created using interview notes and the audio/video recordings, the online platform Airtable was used to tag each extract with broad themes. Extracts were then tagged for contextual info (e.g. Connecting to the public) and then for specific thematic concepts (e.g. Encouraging activism). This process, known as grounded

qualitative coding⁶, allows for deep exploration and analysis of qualitative data. Using these codes, extracts were then re-clustered according to 8 overarching themes: Goals, Needs, Problems, Project Cycles, Tools, Data, Community, and Terminology.

Interview main outcomes

In general, the interviews echoed many insights from the digital ethnography, such as a desire to do more participatory research, a desire for more resources (e.g. tutorials, knowledge sharing), funding issues, poor findability of citizen science projects, the need for hybrid spaces to create opportunities for interdisciplinary skill and knowledge sharing, the importance of division of labor within teams, and the crucial role of a local aspect to create value and passion for projects.

Interesting differences between the Researcher and Non-Researcher groups emerged according to each theme. In terms of goals, researchers tended to focus more on humanitarian goals, while non-researchers mentioned the importance of practical results like laws, apps, or art. Researchers' needs highlighted a need for dissemination support and feedback for validation. Non-researchers on the other hand stressed a need for encouragement, satisfaction, and flexibility in regards to tools and project management. The main challenges for researchers stemmed from a lack of mutual understanding, due to differences in disciplines and country-level approaches, and sharing work in a satisfying way. Non-researchers instead talked about problems understanding each other on a personal level, the challenges of finding time to share work on social media, and the multitude of bureaucratic issues encountered when collaborating.

In general, community did not emerge as a very important aspect for either group, however, a few cases in the non-researcher group did express deeper involvement in participatory research communities, describing them as places where they create friendships with similarly impassioned collaborators. For researchers, however, Twitter represented the main source of community within their field.

On the topic of terminology used to describe collaborative and participatory science projects, researchers tended to use structure-based terms such as co-creation, equality, and citizen scholarship, reflecting the professional and academic lens through which they view participatory science. Non-researchers focused more on goal-based terminology, defining these collaborative projects as sources of engagement, passion, and providing a crucial role in unlocking history.

Clearly, professional researchers and non-academic researchers engage in this topic for different reasons, however, some common themes emerged as well. Bridging the two typologies of potential users, both groups discussed the following:

- A desire for more public involvement
- Reaching a wider public and methods of spreading awareness
- Language/communication issues between researchers and non-researchers/public
- Pushing for Extreme Citizen Science: egalitarian, mutual-learning and collective work practices as methodological and community values
- Non-researchers bring essential skills and knowledge to the table
- Both researchers and non-researchers alike turn to scientific literature for help and

⁶ Strauss, A.L., & Corbin, J. (1990). Basics of qualitative research: Grounded theory procedures and techniques. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

- resources when collaborating on projects
- Both groups want to help each other: researchers want to empower citizens and give back, non-researchers want to deliver quality data to researchers
- Technical roles, public relations and project managers needed
- Creating a shared language is necessary to enable collaboration

Returning to the research questions that informed the user research phase, the interviews provided some insightful answers (See Table 1). These insights, along with the other results of analysis, then allowed for a systematic approach to the user research deliverables described in the following section.

Research Question	Insight Gathered from Interviews
R1. How do non-academics and professional researchers tackle projects differently?	Non-academics generally tackle projects with more practical goals in mind, organizing physical manifestations of their work, as well as volunteering out of passion and vested interest in the topic. Researchers begin collaborations looking for greater and more meaningful public involvement, using an egalitarian and collective work spirit, and working to improve themselves and research by collaborating with non-researchers.
R2. What goals do researchers have when they advocate for participatory science?	They're looking for direct, immediate feedback internally and externally, especially at the beginning of a project, after research and analysis stages, and after delivering results.
R3. What aspects improve user morale while contributing to Citizen Science and, in particular, SSH projects?	Getting feedback, comradery, moments of divulgation, and feeling a sense of achievement all contribute to user morale.
R4. What barriers exist for participatory scientists in terms of scientific literacy?	Language issues appear to be most relevant when delivering results - material must be adapted, and some channels are better than others. Hybrid figures and spaces might help close the gap.
R5. Is a sense of community important for Participatory Science?	While many people value ideas of community, there are very few successful examples as most don't actively participate.

R6. How do research teams naturally form on existing platforms?	Long-term and recurring collaborations in both academic and non-academic spheres represent the most common way teams form.
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Table 1 - Research questions answered

Quote	Interviewee	Interview co...	Rating	Sentiment	Tags	Descriptive Code
195 Transmitting knowledge about an experience is a give and take process. You often receive an interesting challenge from non-researchers.	PR6		★★★★	Positive	ideas steps feedback people	Connecting with the public
196 Speaking about involving the general public, we're missing a tool to involve citizens and disseminate work.	PR8		★★★★	Negative	needs tools communication results problems people	Connecting with the public
197 It's difficult to get feedback internally, but it's important during brown bags and seminars when you give an overview of the project. Some entities are especially difficult to get feedback from like police departments.	PR2		★★★	Negative	needs steps feedback people problems	Connecting with the public
198 I also use Twitter and ResearchGate to publish results.	PR4		★★★	Neutral	needs steps feedback communication results tools	Connecting with the public
199 Volunteers need recognition. This can happen through events, writing, blogs and publishing interviews about the citizen scholars. We are going to start a podcast about our activities soon. Giving recognition to them creates trust and can convinc...	PR9		★★★★	Positive	feedback ideas people communication wants needs	Due credit
200 There's also a problem with recognizing the datasheets and datasets produced by citizen scholars. Through blog posts we try to highlight these aspects, which can also be good as a networking tool.	PR9		★★★★	Negative	wants ideas feedback tools results people data problems	Due credit
201 We use these tools for research because they're easy to install, Transkribus has the typical cloud benefits.	PR3		★★★	Positive	needs tools	Good tools

Figure 2 - User Interview analysis

User research deliverables

User research deliverables were constructed from the themes which directly emerged from the interview analysis, namely: Goals, Needs, Problems, Project Cycles, Tools, Data, Community, Terminology. By clustering coded extracts within these categories, cohesive user profiles formed, each containing a blend of user interviews. In this way, the resulting personas⁷ formed a better representation of potential VERA users.

⁷ Developed by Cooper as part of his “goal-directed design” process, personas encapsulate hypothetical users. They do so by envisioning a multi-dimensional person behind the needs and intentions of a target user base. With a name and face behind the issue, personas can be very practical for guiding design choices and business strategies, if properly implemented. (Cooper, A. (1999). The inmates are running the asylum. In Software-Ergonomie'99 (pp. 17-17). Vieweg+ Teubner Verlag, Wiesbaden.)

Personas

In the end, five personas emerged from the data, reflecting distinct goals, needs, and challenges. Each persona was ascribed a tagline to summarize their key characteristics, for example, in the case of Fernando: "The criminology academic exploring participatory research for the first time". Basic demographic data was also used, inspired by the types of people interviewed during the user research phase. Personas were assigned tools and platforms used, broken down into those used for sharing, collaboration, and others such as Facebook or Academia.edu. Skills in the areas of research, analysis, technical tools, and social media also factored into the design of the personas to evaluate some of the key attributes that emerged from the interviews. (Personas are listed in Annex III).

Scenarios

To better enter into the perspective of each persona, scenarios were written in order to encapsulate their goals, needs, and challenges in a more descriptive way. The purpose of scenarios relates to creating divergent solutions that describe how and when VERA could be useful. By creating detailed descriptions, we were able to lend more realism to the personas that gave a clearer picture of their methods and specific project objectives, providing ideas on how VERA could help achieve them.

Modifications

User research artifacts such as personas and scenarios are not meant to be static. Their usefulness lies in their ability to accurately depict target users, and so when a new insight hints at a fatal flaw in these deliverables, changes should be made to reflect this learning. One such insight came from discussions with WP5 leaders and the project coordinator during the first WP3 workshop held in Pisa on 17 November 2021. Originally, the terms "researcher" or "non-researcher" were applied as labels to each persona to denote their belonging to one of the macro-categories used to guide the interviews. However, the user research and discussion of the results made it abundantly clear that although citizens may not consider themselves academic researchers, they nonetheless bring important forms of research to the project. One of the goals of participatory research, as envisioned within COESO, is to put all collaborators on the same level, therefore, to better reflect this, the term "engaged stakeholder" was proposed as a way to refer to potential users. As a direct impact on the personas, a more descriptive tagline and workplace was added to give context to their professions, without labeling them as a researcher or non-researcher.

Fernando

The criminology academic exploring participatory research for the first time

Age 49
Location Rome, Italy
Job Professor
Work Place Sapienza University of Rome
Expertise Criminology

Tools

Sharing Teams & Owncloud
Collab ML, Python, Kaggle
Other Academia.edu

Skills

Research ●●●
Analysis ●●●
Technical Tools ●●●
Social Media ●●●

“Societal issues should be a top priority from the start of a project”

Background

Fernando has been in academia for about 15 years, so **he knows how disconnected it is from the lives of regular people**. Having always worked within the academic world, **he’s not sure how much public involvement he might need** during projects, but now he’s **committed to an open dialogue with non-academics**.

Scenario

Fernando has an idea to continue a previous study on crime in Rome. He wants to **use VERA to find new collaborators** and stop the cyclical nature of working with the same group of academics. He finds it useful that he can search by skill set to see what a potential collaborator can bring to the project. **Using VERA he manages to build a 5 person team** with another researcher, a political analyst, an anti-corruption advocacy group member and an investigative journalist. He **invites the team members to a newly created project** on VERA. The scope of the project is to do some semi-structured interviews and launch a survey to understand how Romans feel affected by criminal enterprises.

He then **organizes a brainstorming session** to decide what direction the project will take and define responsibilities. Fernando uses the outcomes of the brainstorming to plan the next activities: **he adds a tool to manage the project**, creates milestones, and assigns tasks to the teammates. Thanks to this **definition of roles**, he focuses on coordination and can take part in the discussions created online, while another teammate takes care of networking with journalists and PR.

The team has a really varied set of background skills, which has been a problem for Fernando in the past. **VERA helps him make sure everyone understands each other** by using goal-based terminology like “public engagement”, instead of “dissemination”. On VERA he also finds a workshop guide that he uses with the team to align everyone on what it means to conduct socially meaningful research.

As the project progresses, he is quite satisfied with the collaboration with the team members and decides to **add them to his VERA network for future collaborations**.

During the interview analysis Fernando and its team have developed a new transcription pipeline. At the end of the project they share it on Kaggle along with the data they’ve collected. He wants to share the model with people outside of the VERA project and find like-minded collaborators to suggest code improvements.

Goals

- Make work more accessible to the wider public
- **Explore participatory research** to bridge worlds and understand how research can be more useful for his own work and society
- Create a space with opportunities for more collaborations with citizens
- **Understand and use skills non-researchers bring to a project** for better integration
- **Contribute to an active community** and utilize the resources it provides

Needs

- New ways of reaching the public, not for crowdsourcing data but to **create an exchange**
- More awareness of interdisciplinary skillsets that could help his research
- **An intermediary for networking, organizational strategy, PR and to interface with journalists**
- Open source, adaptable tools with **institutional level security**

Challenges

- **Unable to connect with the public** through traditional methods
- Creating **common ground between collaborators** with different approaches from varied backgrounds and cultures
- Critical of academic values
- **No time for dissemination** on social media
- Tools aren’t modifiable and aren’t designed with researchers in mind

Figure 3 - Example of VERA persona

Co-design workshops

Co-design workshops are a heterogeneous type of activities that can be used with different scopes and in different phases of a project. In COESO, we planned to organize and conduct workshops to involve end-users in the design of the VERA platform. Although very heterogeneous, the common factor of workshops is that they involve people as active contributors, and not just as listeners. In the case of COESO, these people are members of the pilot teams and potential users of the platform. In fact, even if the designers of the team are those in charge of the design of the platform, the whole project team and, most importantly, end-users are called to impact the project design.

The exact topics and number of workshops to be held were not decided in advance, leaving the team the freedom to pick the most relevant problems to investigate, as these arise during the various phases of the design process.

The scope of the workshops is to elicit direct feedback from the participants about aspects regarding their previous experience with participatory science, their understanding of the design, and their expectations for what concerns the improvements that the VERA platform should bring to their projects. Workshop facilitators, that belong to the COESO design team, have the role of involving all the participants equally, and stimulating a prolific discussion among them, to make common needs emerge from the conversation.

A fundamental requirement of workshops is that they must provide actionable outcomes that can be used by the team during the design process or to improve what has already been designed.

We recently organized our first co-design workshop in February this year involving 6 persons from the pilot teams. The details of the first workshop are provided in the section below.

Due to the current pandemic situation, the first workshop was held online using Zoom as the main communication system and FigJam as the virtual whiteboard. To decide if the next workshops will be planned as virtual or in-person events, we will take into account the following conditions:

1. The evolution of the pandemic and related regulations.
2. The possibility to co-locate in-person workshops during other COESO events.
3. The ability to recruit participants for in-person or online events.

To improve the organization of workshops, we sent a brief survey to the pilot team members asking for some basic information that will be useful to plan the next events. Here are the main takeaways from the survey:

- The favored duration for a workshop is **2 hours**. This is the optimal duration to help participants in fitting the event into their agenda.
- The best way to schedule a workshop is by using the platform **Doodle**.
- Participants have a **computer with a mouse or trackpad** at their disposal. This means that we can use virtual whiteboarding tools like FigJam without worrying about the limitations of a tablet or smartphone.

First workshop

The scope of the first workshop was to investigate which external tools the users of VERA would like to have at their disposal on the platform. VERA will be a web platform that will facilitate collaboration and it will be centered around participatory science projects. Since collaboration nowadays already happens on a multitude of digital services and tools, we are not going to reinvent these tools from scratch, but rather integrate into VERA those that users already use in their daily routine.

We foresee two levels of tool integration in VERA:

- **Light integration:** tools are made available to the users of VERA in the form of external links that bring the user to the page of each tool. These tools are used outside of VERA with no integration.
- **Deep integration:** tools are more integrated into VERA through their APIs. Also, these tools will be used outside of VERA but some feedback and information will be made available inside the platform.

Participants in the workshop were asked to list the tools and services they have used in their previous and current collaboration projects and those they would like to find available in the VERA platform. Since the number of participants was limited, we looked for qualitative results and the expected takeaway as the most useful categories of tools to be integrated into VERA.

Workshop information

- **Number of participants:** 6
- **Duration:** 3 hours

- **Day:** 1st February 2022
- **Facilitators:** Bill Costello - Net7, Giulio Andreini - Net7

Methodology

Warm-up

The workshop started with a couple of warm-up activities. First, we asked all the participants to introduce themselves, get to know each other, and gain some confidence with the virtual dashboard we were using (FigJam). This first activity also provided the opportunity to fix some technical issues that emerged at the beginning of the workshop. Then, we did a brief and general introduction to the COESO project and explained what is the scope of the VERA platform.

Figure 4 - COESO introduction at the workshop

Post-up ideation

During the main part of the workshop, we asked participants to write on the virtual post-its the name of the tools and services they used in their previous collaborative projects, and those they would like to find in VERA. We asked them the following questions:

- "What tools and services have you used for past collaborations with your peers?"
- "What tools and services do you expect to find in VERA?"

We asked to write the name of the various tools on post-its and to stick them on a storyboard that divided the project lifecycle into 5 steps:

- Project idea
- Building the team
- Funding
- During the project
- End of the project and sharing results

Then we asked participants to present their ideas to the group, to better share their perspective with the others, and to investigate how each tool can be useful for collaboration during each given phase on the project.

While the participants were presenting their post-its, the facilitators clustered the tools creating categories that grouped similar tools (i.e. Mattermost and Slack are considered to belong to the same category). This allowed us to have a limited number of tools and services categories, as a result of the ideation process.

Figure 5 - The storyboard that we used to understand which tools are used in each phase of a project

The following categories were identified:

- Blog (i.e. WordPress)
- Calendars (i.e. Google Calendar, Apple Calendar)
- Email
- File storage and sharing (i.e. Google Drive, Dropbox)
- Graphic processors (i.e. Canva, Photoshop)
- Mailing lists
- Mobile instant messaging (i.e. WhatsApp, Telegram)
- Personal notes (i.e. Evernote)
- Phone
- Presentation tools (i.e. Powerpoint, Google Slides)
- Professional networks (i.e. LinkedIn)
- Search tools (i.e. Google, RSS feeds)
- Spreadsheets (i.e. Microsoft Excel, Google Spreadsheets)
- Meeting scheduling (i.e. Doodle, Framadate)
- Social networks (i.e. Twitter, Facebook)
- Video conference (i.e. Zoom, Google Meet)
- Web communication platforms (i.e. Slack, Mattermost)
- Word processors (i.e. Microsoft Word, Google Documents)

In the final part of the workshop, participants were assigned 4 votes each and were asked to vote on the categories of tools they felt were most important to their work. This helped us provide prioritization to the workshop results.

And the winner is...

Figure 6 - Most voted tools

Key takeaways

To be sure to get the most out of the workshop, we also reviewed the FigJam board and we counted how many times the tools belonging to each category were mentioned. We were able to build a ranking with the most mentioned tools.

Figure 7 - Most mentioned tools ranking

At this point, we had two different perspectives on the workshop outcomes: the voting and counting of mentions. We decided to build a scatter chart to intersect these two dimensions and have a visual view of the most useful category of tools to integrate into VERA.

The scatter chart (Figure 8) depicts the final results of the workshop, displaying the categories of tools and services that participants expect to find in VERA. The categories at the top right are those that had more votes and were mentioned the most. In any case, we consider all the categories in this chart to be the most relevant. Many other categories were left out due to the absence of voting or a limited number of mentions.

This is a qualitative result and has no statistical or quantitative value due to the limited number of participants. However, it still provides a very valuable indication of the tools we have to take into consideration for the VERA platform in its first development.

Figure 8 - Plot with number of times a tool category was voted vs. mentioned during the workshop

Impact on the VERA design

The outcomes of the workshops will be used by the project team in the following ways:

- The categories that emerged from the workshop will be the ones that will be integrated in VERA.
- The categorization will be used to group tools in the VERA interface.
- Most of the tools mentioned during the workshop will be integrated into VERA. We will also take into account other tools (but still belonging to the aforementioned categories).
- The suggested tools will be evaluated to understand if it's possible to implement a deep integration into VERA (thus showing feedback and information from the tool directly in VERA).

Further workshops

An important problem that arose during the design process is how to communicate what VERA is and its functionalities to a wide group of users, ranging from academic researchers to journalists to citizens. These types of users are accustomed to different languages and vocabularies, but it's crucial that the text and communication of VERA speaks a common language that all target users can understand. For this reason, we plan to hold a workshop dedicated to this topic, to improve the vocabulary we will use in the interface of the platform.

We will plan other workshops if other important issues arise during the design process, and we will involve participants from the second batch of pilot projects.

Co-design and alignment with WP5

While WP3 is dedicated to the actual design of the VERA platform, WP5 is devoted to cooperation quality assessment, with the development and implementation of cooperation analytics that will be analyzed through a dashboard developed by FNSP-CEE and linked from VERA.

Given that the VERA platform is the actual place where the cooperation will take place and analyzed, it is natural that the two work packages are strictly related and need to proceed very closely with seamless integration and alignment. In this sense, a series of specific workshops are periodically being organized during the project lifespan in relation to critical moments of the overall progress.

After a series of conference calls in the initial months, a first WP3/WP5 workshop was organized and physically took place on 17 November 2021 in Pisa, Italy.

The aim of the workshop was to present the cooperation analytics needs and initial recommendations, match them with the personas and use case scenarios that emerged from the user interviews analysis, and discuss and plan the VERA architecture in relation with the cooperation analytics. One important outcome was the definition of the non-academic target audience as “engaged stakeholders”, instead of distinguishing between academic researchers and non.

A second specific workshop, organized remotely on 24 March 2022, focused on the design of the profile pages in VERA. The discussion started from the review of the profile page designed within

the TRIPLE project⁸, to understand which features could be reused in the design of VERA and if this structure could be functional to the needs of WP5.

Further alignment activities will take place in the upcoming months upon necessity and will be devoted specifically to understanding where to integrate and access the cooperation analytics platform within VERA, in terms of architecture but also in terms of UX and UI.

V. User experience

User stories definition

User stories represent the first concrete steps that transform research insights into design indications. Using the personas and scenarios as an overall guide, user stories were defined to describe the technical features required to accomplish the activities outlined.

These user stories derived from “epic” stories used to give the overall objective of each persona, given their well-defined scenario. By breaking down the epic stories into smaller tasks for each persona, we were able to define four principal areas in VERA for the user experience, each with specific activities in mind.

- **The VERA Hub:** a place for recruiting collaborators, matching with projects, communicating with other users, sharing ideas, debating, accessing training resources, and finding funding
- **The Project Page:** for communicating with team members, storing project materials, sharing files, planning the project, debating with team members, working collaboratively, and adding/removing integrated project tools
- **The Personal Workspace:** a personal section for communicating with select members, sharing personal work, working independently, adding/removing integrated personalized tools
- **The Profile:** a section for updating personal information, checking feedback/notifications, integrating accounts, and managing tools

With these sections of VERA defined, and user stories detailing some feature requirements, the next step involved choosing a select few user stories with which to start sketching.

⁸ <https://www.gotriple.eu/>

PERSONA	Count	Steps	Section	Necessity (MoSCoW)	Notes
Fernando	Count 11				
30	Create project	Create new project Add skillset requirements to project	Project Dashboard	Must have	
31	Create draft project	Create draft project Add skillset requirements to project Post draft project to VERA hub	VERA Hub	Should have	
32	Connect with collaborators to hold brainstorming session	Accept collaborator requests Contact collaborators Create meeting	Project Dashboard	Must have	Ability to create meeting in dashboard would facilitate process
33	Set up project dashboard	Open project dashboard Open widget library Add kanban widget Add timeline widget Add public engagement widget	Project Dashboard	Should have	Wizard to guide users to add common project widgets (mini-tools) like kanbans, timelines, tables. Public engagement to collect info for social media posts and possibly post directly to social ...
34	Explore suggested resources so that he can hold a workshop to align the team	Open VERA hub View resources section Search workshop suggestions	VERA Hub	Could have	

Figure 9 - User stories

Setting priorities

In the design and development of VERA, we want to follow agile principles. Our plan is to organize the project in iterations to release incremental versions of the platform. We want to avoid releasing the first and final version of the platform at the end of the project. Instead, we prefer to release a first minimum viable product (MVP) to make it available to the pilot teams and to the public as soon as possible. This MVP will then be subjected to testing through a dedicated user testing phase, the results of which will be used to make necessary additions and improve the platform⁹.

We reviewed the user stories to prioritize and schedule them following these principles:

- User stories that respond to the user needs that emerged in the user research phase.
- User stories that allow the pilots teams to start collaborating on their projects.
- User stories which respond to the major requirements of the project proposal.

The user stories that we identified for the first design and development iteration are:

Who	What	Why
As a user	I want to register to VERA	to create a project and have access to all its functionalities
As a researcher or engaged	I want to create a project	to invite the project

⁹At least 2 usability testing sessions will take place to validate the interface.

stakeholder		collaborators and start working on the project
As a project coordinator	I want to invite my collaborators to VERA	to take advantage of all the functionalities and improve our collaboration
As a project member	I want to chat with the other members	to better coordinate the activities, to stay updated on what the others are doing, and to have faster communication

Table 2 - User stories definition

The project backlog contains other user stories that will be considered for successive iterations.

VI. User interface design

The outcomes of all the previous activities (benchmarking, user interviews, personas, scenarios, user stories, and the first workshop) allowed the Net7 team to start designing the interface of VERA. The design process is a sequence of iterations of ideation/sketching, wireframing, design of high-fidelity mockups, development, and evaluation.

To date, we've been going through the first design iteration and handed-off the mockups to the development team for the implementation of what will be the first alpha release of VERA. In the following section we will illustrate the work done.

Wireframes

From the outcomes of the research phase, we started designing the wireframes of the user interface. Wireframes are a simplified version of each page, designed using grayscale colors and basic fonts: they are useful to understand the logical structure of each page, which chunks of information to include, their hierarchy, and their relations in space. Wireframes provide the team a first perspective on each page, and allow raising usability problems to fix, and getting closer (through iterations) to what will be the final structure.

For the design on VERA, we started by focusing on the user stories with higher priority and designing all the related interfaces and interactions.

The sections we designed are:

- Homepage for non-logged and logged users:** the homepage shows users how VERA can support them in their collaborative projects and what are the main features of the platform. The homepage contains a main call-to-action that guides users into the creation of their projects. In the future, when there will be some registered users and some existing projects, we will update the homepage design to show some of the user-generated contents of the platform.

- **Onboarding/Profiling journey:** users are guided through this journey to create their profile which includes their interests, their skills, and their spoken languages. This information is crucial to allow the system to suggest users the projects for which they could be a good fit (this will be handled by the match-making system¹⁰).
- **Project creation journey:** a wizard that guides the users in the creation of their projects. During this journey, we ask users for the basic information that is necessary to set-up the project.
- **Project:** this will be the most important section in VERA, where the actual collaboration on projects will happen. The main sections of each project will be:
 - **Messaging integration:** page dedicated to the communication among the team members. The messaging will be powered by the open-source platform [Mattermost](#) and in VERA users will have at their disposal a simplified version of the messaging system. Then they will have the possibility to navigate to Mattermost to exploit its full features.
 - **Team management:** this section will allow to invite users directly via email, and to define the profiles needed for the projects to enable the match-making system to find potential collaborators.
 - **External tools list:** here, users will find the list of all of the external tools suggested by VERA. Tools will be grouped in categories and will also be proposed to the users during the various phases of the project.
 - **Resources:** VERA will provide users with a list of links to external resources that can help them in their projects. These resources will range from general information about citizen and participatory science, to detailed guides related to the various issues that can be encountered during a project lifecycle (management, dissemination, funding).
 - **Project's settings:** this section will allow the project administrator to change the settings and information of the project.
 - **Project suggestions and checklist:** the project section will also include a checklist and a sequence of tips that will help project members to progress in the project by proposing activities to plan in during each phase.

Below are some designed wireframes which have been handed-off to the engineering team for development.

¹⁰ Developed under Task 3.3, the match-making service in VERA will aim at finding the best possible candidates for a specific project by considering the classification of the project on the one hand and the skills and interests of the user on the other, and by considering the textual descriptions, provided both for presenting the project and for the profile of the users.

Collaborate smarter to face societal challenges together

Collaborate with others easily, engage in discussion and share results to make a real impact in the community.

Let's Collaborate

VERA Helps

Start a citizen science project and fill the roles you need

VERA lets you define the types of skills you need to match you with people who are interested in starting a project and are open to collaborate. Just want to find a project? Sign up to explore projects looking for people like you!

Engage with like-minded people and get past the technical jargon

Chat, collaborate and organize events with skilled people who have the same passion as you. VERA not only helps you work together, but it also helps get everyone speaking the same lingo and connect better with the general public.

Bring tools together into a single space and optimize your workflow

Keep the tools you already know and love. VERA will help you organize them. Manage notes and materials so you can focus more on the project and less on project management.

The VERA Advantage

Synchronize Your Team
Set meetings with automatic invites for your team. Get reminders in VERA to schedule new ones so your team is always up-to-date.

Work Together
Connect your collaboration tools or use VERA to make files more accessible. Seamlessly talk to teammates with the integrated chat.

Connect with the Public
VERA provides a platform to deliver high quality results. Spread awareness and get more people involved in the project.

VERA Integrates With

**Collaborate.
Chat.
Share Results.**

Start Collaborating

Figure 10 - VERA homepage wireframe

A Criminological Study on Businesses in Rome ▼
 Not Public

Home

Messaging

Team

Services

Resources

Settings

Welcome to VERA

Tips to Get Started Hide

Skip for now

Invite Team Members

Quickly send project invitations to people you know and track invites, all within VERA

Send Invitations

Skip for now

Make Your Team Wishlist

Add the roles and skills you need and VERA's matchmaking system will find them!

Create Wishlist

>

My Checklist

- Invite members
- Team wishlist
- Project details
- Make a project introduction video
- Add collaboration tools
- Kickoff project with the team
- Publish project
- Write your first diary post

VERA Features Demo Hide

A Criminological Study on Businesses in Rome ▼
 Not Public

Home

Messaging

Team

Services

Resources

Settings

Welcome to VERA

Tips to Get Started Hide

Skip for now

Invite Team Members

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Make Your Team Wishlist

Add the roles and skills you need and VERA's matchmaking system will find them!

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My checklist

- Invite members
- Team wishlist
- Project details
- Make a project introduction video
- Add collaboration tools
- Kickoff project with the team
- Publish project
- Write your first diary post

VERA Features Demo Hide

Figure 11, 12 -Project dashboard wireframes

 A Criminological Study on Businesses in Rome ▼
Not Public

- Home
- Messaging**
- Team
- Services
- Resources
- Settings

Project Chat

[See more on Mattermost](#) →

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—

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—

 —
—

Write something...

 A Criminological Study on Businesses in Rome ▼
Not Public

- Home
- Messaging**
- Team
- Services
- Resources
- Settings

Project Chat

[See more on Mattermost](#) →

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—

Write something...

Figure 13,14 - VERA project messaging system wireframes

User interface

To design the final look and feel of VERA, we decided to start from the design of the GoTriple platform. As VERA, and also GoTriple, will be incorporated as a service under OPERAS, we would like the two platforms to be coherent and communicate to the users that they belong to the same ecosystem.

Compared to the GoTriple UI Kit, we decided to keep the original structure of the components that will also be useful in VERA, to use a similar font stack, and the same structural colors (grayscale color palette used for background and borders). The brand colors of GoTriple (red, yellow, and purple) will be replaced by the branding colors of VERA.

The components from the GoTriple UI Kit that will be reused in VERA are:

- Basic elements: pagination, user thumb, metadata, card, dropdown
- Buttons
- Tags: discipline, keyword, counter
- Header
- User profiles previews
- Modals
- Form elements
- Navigation elements: tab bar and vertical navigation
- Wizard element
- Profile completion indicator

VII. Next steps: User evaluation

User evaluation is another way to involve end-users in the design process. While UX research activities (interviews and co-design workshops) happen at the beginning of the design, evaluation techniques can be used during the process and allow the team to assess the usability of what has been designed.

User evaluation can be divided in two main branches:

- Qualitative evaluation: it allows us to investigate how users interact with the design through testing and observations. These techniques don't provide statistical results but a lot of qualitative insights, since they allow us to see the product with the eyes of the user.
- Quantitative evaluation: it is a group of methodologies based on quantitative data retrieved from the users interactions on the actual online platform. This data provides a valuable and realistic perspective on how users interact with a product, usage metrics, and highlight usability and traction problems. The tools used to run this type of investigation include Google Analytics (or similar platforms) and Mixpanel (used for retention and funnel analysis).

In the next phases of the COESO project, we will apply both qualitative and quantitative evaluation methodologies.

For qualitative evaluation, we plan to run 2 or more usability testing sessions involving groups of 5 people each. Participants will be asked to accomplish a given set of tasks (usually between 10 and 15) using an interactive prototype or the online platform. The observation of the behavior of the users and what they say during the test, will provide us insights of the usability problems that need to be fixed.

For quantitative analysis, we will integrate Google Analytics and Mixpanel to track the users behavior and the retention of the platform. This type of analysis will require a larger amount of data, so it will become valuable once the platform is live and used by a decent number of users. Also quantitative data will provide useful information about possible usability problems and will suggest strategies to improve the overall user experience.

VIII. Plan for the implementation and development

By utilizing an Agile approach, our plan moving forward is that after the completion of each design cycle, pages and sections within VERA shall be marked for hand-off to the developers. This way, development and design can work in tandem, iteratively implementing features and developing them, in order of the feature priority previously outlined. Another benefit to this work style lies in the quicker turnaround for identifying feasibility issues or the need to fine tune any previously designed elements. This hand-off has already begun with the homepage and shows promising signs in terms of optimizing the delivery of a beta version of the VERA platform.

IX. Conclusions

The user research activities performed under Task 3.1 are of paramount importance to look at the design of the VERA platform from the perspective of real users.

This is a fundamental approach to the design of any product or service. Takeaways from the first workshop and from the ones that will be planned in the upcoming months (including the one focusing on the vocabulary) will be the primary inputs for the finalization of the VERA design.

Designers of the user experience and of the interface will select the ideas that are feasible and relevant for the scope of the COESO project and will integrate them into the design of the VERA interface.

The partners adopted the agile methodology whose core is an iterative approach: the plan is to organize the project and VERA delivery in iterations to release incremental versions of the platform. We want to avoid releasing the first and final version of the platform at the end of the

project. Instead, we prefer to release a first minimum version to make it available to the pilot teams and to the public as soon as possible to collect feedback and improve the platform itself as much as possible before the end of the project itself.

The strict cooperation established between WP3 and WP5 will be kept throughout the overall development and release of the VERA platform and of the cooperation analytics dashboard.

The benchmark analysis carried out as well as the continuous interaction with the Citizen Science community at large are proving that the VERA platform has the huge potential to become the reference platform in Europe to highlight and support the Citizen Science practices into SSH disciplines, and its development is taking place in a particularly fruitful moment in which the understanding of the transversal and complementary role that SSH can have in Citizen Science projects is growing.

Annexes

Annex I - Sample of benchmark matrix

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M
1	Type	Name	Website	Objectives/Challenges addressed	Why It's relevant for COESO	Login/Sign Up	General Notes	Onboarding/Tutorials	Project Management	Data	Resources	Tools	Candidate for Further Benchmarking (Sign Up, Test etc.)
2	Platforms	EU-Citizen.Science	http://eu-citizen.science.eu	central platform for citizen science in Europe. A source of standards and criteria for citizen science. A repository for citizen science resources. A network of networks for citizen science. A place to find training opportunities	SwafS projects, Community, Horizon2020	Yes	Top menu navigation with Search, About, Blog Events, Forum, Moocs, Open Call, Add project, and prominent filterable project search. Easy to find organizations associated with CS	Training resources highlighted on homepage	Via profile, however projects are hosted on external sites	Not provided through website/platform	MOOCS section in top menu. Filtering by Resources provides guidelines, texts, best practices in multiple languages	Training modules	YES
3	Platforms	CitieS-Health	https://citiehealth.eu/	The project will create an interactive toolkit with customised tools and best practices for the replication of the studies in other locations by researchers, individuals and citizen group in the field of environmental epidemiology	SwafS projects, European pilots	No	Top menu navigation with About, Get involved, Resources, News and Go to the Toolkit! Add your Story section to upload a toolkit!	Toolkit section explains process	Not provided through website/platform	Not provided through website/platform	Resources section in top menu. Limited to resources produced by projects	Co-design workshop guides, research project walkthrough guides	NO
4	Platforms	MICS	https://mics.tools/	Developing metrics and instruments to evaluate citizen-science impacts on the environment and society	SwafS projects, Horizon2020, Developing very similar web-platform	No	Top menu navigation with About, News, Resources, Case studies and MICS Labs. Links to Code4Cloud and ECISA. Luigi Ceccaroni (scientific coordinator) seen posting in EU-Citizen.Science forums.	From Homepage link to learn more about Citizen Zenodo	Not provided through website/platform	Not provided through website/platform. Accessible through Zenodo.	Homepage provides some resources. Resources section in top menu links to deliverables on Zenodo.	Co-design flyer, factheets, toolbox documentation, and other deliverables hosted on zenodo	NO
5	Platforms	SSHOPENCLOUD	https://sshopencloud.eu/	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) is a project funded by the EU framework programme Horizon 2020 and unites 20 partner organisations and their 27 associates in developing the social sciences and humanities area of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).	SSH focus, SwafS projects, Horizon2020	Yes (trainer account and regular account)	Top menu navigation with About, Marketplace, Training, Resources, SSHOC in Action, News & Events bootcamps, a link to the SSH training community, and SSH training discovery toolkit	Training sections provides workshops & webinars, "train-the-trainer" bootcamps, a link to the SSH training community, and SSH training discovery toolkit	Not provided through website/platform	Service catalogue section in Marketplace provides links to data management systems for surveys, metadata conversion services, as well as online survey databases, survey corpora and audio transcript data	Training section provides help resources. Resources section in top menu with deliverables, awareness raising events, scientific publications, white papers, posters, videos and communications kit	Data management, networking, processing & analysis (e.g. automated verification tool to verify translations), security and operations, storage and training tools.	YES
6	Platforms	SUPER_MoRRI	https://www.super-moerri.eu/super-moerri/index.php	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> establish an RRI indicator hub drawing in data streams from a connected network of projects, and creating a user-friendly, interactive dashboard, which will provide easy access for multiple stakeholders and allow for selective extraction of data based on user needs and interests. take a co-creation approach by involving a range of stakeholders for exploring, developing, testing, and validating and RRI self-assessment practice; interaction with international partners beyond Europe 	SwafS projects, Horizon2020, Developing similar web platform	No	Top menu navigation with The Project, About Us, Our Network, Our Poits, Actions, Contact Us. EU-Citizen Science, MICS and SISCODE are part of Super MoRRI ecosystem. Super MoRRI stresses international partnerships	Not provided through website/platform	Not provided through website/platform	MoRRI network map	Findings section with reports related to project. MoRRI 2014-2018 section provides publications. Actions section provides webinars and workshops from past events.	Stakeholder workshop from past Super MoRRI event	NO

Annex II - Consent form

INFORMATION SHEET AND CONSENT FORM

Project title: COESO (Collaborative Engagement on Societal Issues)

Researcher name(s): XXX

What is the research about?

We're inviting you to help us with research for the project, COESO. This European Union funded project aims to help with collaboration **in the field of Social Sciences and Humanities research**. To accomplish this goal, we aim to interview both **field experts and non-professional researchers**, at different career stages and from different European countries. These interviews will help us better understand the needs of end-users and aid in building the best possible platform.

Our project deals with Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) research and the goal is to build a digital platform that facilitates and supports participatory research (also known as Citizen Science) by providing a set of tools to discover potential research partners, define and co-design activities, co-create new knowledge and solutions, and ultimately share it with society.

SSH research is made up of a wide array of disciplines. While the breadth of skills is certainly one of the field's advantages and key features, it also leads to fragmentation that prevents SSH research from reaching its full potential. COESO seeks to address this issue by pushing the boundaries of innovation in public engagement in order to achieve greater collaboration and

mutual learning between SSH sub-disciplines and non-researchers alike. Furthermore, by working with research funding organizations, COESO will attract more financial support to Citizen Science and SSH projects.

This project has received funding from the European Commission, H2020 programme (Project Number: 101006325).

Why participate?

This form has been written to help you decide if you would like to take part and participation is entirely voluntary. It is up to you and you alone whether you wish to take part. If you do decide to take part you will be free to withdraw at any time without providing a reason and without penalty.

What will I be required to do?

You will participate in a **semi-structured qualitative interview**. Questions will be about your research work and about the digital tools you use as part of your work. The answers to these questions will help us in understanding the needs of potential COESO users and in the subsequent design of the platform.

Compensation

There is no compensation for participating in this interview.

How will you handle my data?

Your data will be stored in an pseudonymised form and will only be accessible to Net7 Srl and the partners of COESO for the purpose of completing the project, writing a scientific paper or an article [the research contact person is Giulio Andreini, email: andreini@netseven.it, phone: +393478283609].

This means that a key stored separately will link your research data to your real identity. Your data will be stored in the Net7 Srl servers and local storage, with data fully anonymised at the earliest opportunity (i.e. when data that could identify you is no longer necessary for the purposes of the research). Your contributions to the workshop are treated in the strictest confidence - it will be impossible to identify individuals within a dataset when any of the research is disseminated (e.g. in publications/presentations). Net7 Srl acts as Data Controller (email: ruberti@netseven.it).

Retention of research data

Researchers are obliged to retain research data for up to 10 years post-publication, however your anonymised research data may be retained indefinitely (e.g., so that researchers engage in open practice and other researchers can access their data to confirm the conclusions of published work). Consistent with our data retention policy, researchers retain consent forms for as long as we continue to hold information about a data subject and for 10 years for published research).

Consent statement:

Please consider the following before indicating your consent on this form. Indicating your consent confirms that you are willing to participate in the research, however, indicating consent does not commit you to anything you do not wish to do and you are free to withdraw your participation at any time. You are indicating consent under the following assumptions:

- I understand the contents of the participant information sheet and consent form.
- I have been given the opportunity to ask questions about the research and have had them answered satisfactorily.
- I understand that my participation is entirely voluntary and that I can withdraw from the research (parts of the project or the entire project) at any time without penalty and without having to provide an explanation.
- I understand who has access to my data and how it will be handled at all stages of the research project.

Please tick (X) the boxes	Yes - I do consent	No - I do not consent
I consent to take part in this study conducted by the COESO project who intend to use my data for further research on the design of the COESO platform		
I consent the interview to be recorded and later transcribed for internal research and analysis purposes only		
I consent the interview data to be used in completely anonymised form in scientific publications or presentations		

I confirm that I am willing to take part in this research

PRINT NAME:

SIGNATURE:

DATE:

Privacy notice and legal basis for processing:

Net7 Srl ("we") is committed to protecting the privacy and security of your personal data in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation ("GDPR") (EU) 2016/679 (and any other directly applicable EU regulation relating to privacy, together with "Data Protection Law"). The research team adheres to the principles of the General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR).

For research involving living humans, the Data Controller adheres to, and collects, processes and handles/archives data in compliance with:

Article 6 (1) e: processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller.

Article 9 (2) j: processing is necessary for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes in accordance with Article 89(1) based on Union or Member State law which shall be proportionate to the aim pursued, respect the essence of the right to data protection and provide for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the fundamental rights and the interests of the data subject.

Where applicable, this form is prepared in consultation with Article 13 of EU GDPR legislation, detailing the information to be provided where personal data are collected from the data subject.

If you have concerns about this research, please contact andreini@netseven.it for enquiries. If you are not happy with the way your information is being handled, in the first instance, you should contact the Net7 Srl Data Controller (ruberti@netseven.it). If you remain unhappy with the response received from us, you have the right to lodge a complaint with your national Data Protection Authority (DPA) (full list available here: https://edpb.europa.eu/about-edpb/board/members_en).

Annex III - VERA personas

Fernando

The criminology academic exploring participatory research for the first time

Age 49

Location Rome, Italy

Job Professor

Work Place Sapienza University of Rome

Expertise Criminology

Tools

Sharing Teams & Owncloud

Collab ML, Python, Kaggle

Other Academia.edu

Skills

Research

Analysis

Technical Tools

Social Media

“Societal issues should be a top priority from the start of a project”

Background

Fernando has been in academia for about 15 years, so **he knows how disconnected it is from the lives of regular people**. Having always worked within the academic world, **he’s not sure how much public involvement he might need** during projects, but now he’s **committed to an open dialogue with non-academics**.

Scenario

Fernando has an idea to continue a previous study on crime in Rome. He wants to **use VERA to find new collaborators** and stop the cyclical nature of working with the same group of academics. He finds it useful that he can search by skill set to see what a potential collaborator can bring to the project. **Using VERA he manages to build a 5 person team** with another researcher, a political analyst, an anti-corruption advocacy group member and an investigative journalist. He **invites the team members to a newly created project** on VERA. The scope of the project is to do some semi-structured interviews and launch a survey to understand how Romans feel affected by criminal enterprises.

He then **organizes a brainstorming session** to decide what direction the project will take and define responsibilities. Fernando uses the outcomes of the brainstorming to plan the next activities: **he adds a tool to manage the project**, creates milestones, and assigns tasks to the teammates. Thanks to this **definition of roles**, he focuses on coordination and can take part in the discussions created online, while another teammate takes care of networking with journalists and PR.

The team has a really varied set of background skills, which has been a problem for Fernando in the past. **VERA helps him make sure everyone understands each other** by using goal-based terminology like “public engagement”, instead of “dissemination”. On VERA he also finds a workshop guide that he uses with the team to align everyone on what it means to conduct socially meaningful research.

As the project progresses, he is quite satisfied with the collaboration with the team members and decides to **add them to his VERA network for future collaborations**.

During the interview analysis Fernando and its team have developed a new transcription pipeline. At the end of the project they share it on Kaggle along with the data they’ve collected. He wants to share the model with people outside of the VERA project and find like-minded collaborators to suggest code improvements.

Goals

- Make work more accessible to the wider public
- **Explore participatory research** to bridge worlds and understand how research can be more useful for his own work and society
- Create a space with opportunities for more collaborations with citizens
- **Understand and use skills non-researchers bring to a project** for better integration
- **Contribute to an active community** and utilize the resources it provides

Needs

- New ways of reaching the public, not for crowdsourcing data but to **create an exchange**
- More awareness of interdisciplinary skillsets that could help his research
- An **intermediary for networking, organizational strategy, PR and to interface with journalists**
- Open source, adaptable tools with **institutional level security**

Challenges

- **Unable to connect with the public** through traditional methods
- Creating **common ground between collaborators** with different approaches from varied backgrounds and cultures
- Critical of academic values
- **No time for dissemination** on social media
- Tools aren’t modifiable and aren’t designed with researchers in mind

Eléa

The sociologist with previous experiences in research projects with artists and citizens

Age 34
Location São Paulo, Brazil
Job Sociologist
Work Place Centro Cultural São Paolo
Expertise Statistics

Tools

Sharing Zoom & Dropbox
Collab Office, SPSS, iMovie
Other Twitter

Skills

Research ●●●○
 Analysis ●●●○
 Technical Tools ●●●○
 Social Media ●●●○

“I do research for and with people to make a direct impact in their lives”

Background

After doing participatory research for a few years in Lisbon, Eléa now lives in São Paulo, working for the cultural association Centro Cultural. The large amount of consultation requests means Eléa **needs help from a tool to keep projects organized**. That way she can focus on what she loves: co-creating with citizens to give them more agency in scientific research.

Scenario

Three artists have asked Eléa for help with an **ethnographic study on urban awareness**. They plan to **visually document the most iconic landmarks in the neighborhoods** of Jardins and Itaim Bibi, in São Paulo. To conduct their research they will need to get in touch with the local community by doing interviews, taking pictures, and filming videos.

Eléa, who already has some experience on VERA, **is added to the newly created project** by the three artists. The team needs funding to kick off the project and some help to make contact with the local community. So on VERA, **Eléa gets in touch with Sergi**, who is working for an NGO that is particularly active in those neighborhoods. After exchanging a few messages, they agree on a shared vision of the research, and **she invites Sergi and two of his colleagues to the VERA project**. Looking for funding opportunities on VERA, they find one that seems perfect for them, and they submit a project proposal.

After some weeks, the proposal is accepted and **they finally start the actual work**. Eléa starts by finding some demographic data to help with identifying population segments of interest and **saves some statistics to the project workspace in VERA**. Then, with the support of the NGO team, **they start working in the field**, interviewing people, taking pictures of landmarks, and shooting video footage.

During the project, the team collaborates asynchronously via audio messages on VERA since, for some members, the Internet connection is too slow for Zoom. VERA also makes it easy for Eléa to collect her fieldnotes and save audio recordings in her personal workspace, with a handy tagging system to find things easier.

At the end of the project, they work on an **exhibition at Centro Cultural** in São Paulo where they plan to show photos and a film about the experiences locals have while navigating their neighborhoods. They also make some short clips of the film to **promote the exhibit on Twitter**.

Goals

- Optimize dissemination via shareable content and widely-read publications
- **Increase recruiting capabilities** and enhance awareness of participatory science's power
- Empower citizens through knowledge co-production and local context
- Lend more accountability to research and create more opportunities for feedback
- Get more experience with creating and sharing project outcomes online

Needs

- **To motivate and train collaborators** to support them during work
- Public involvement for project activities
- Help with digital project management, finding collaborators, and handling budgeting
- Financial security throughout the dissemination process
- **Asynchronous collaborative tools** and plenty of storage for videos and images

Challenges

- Overcoming the researcher stereotype when working with citizens
- Dealing with logistics and resource issues
- **Not much faith in dedicated online platforms for dissemination**
- Language gets in the way of collaboration from time to time
- Tools overcomplicate work and can be a barrier for some communities she works with

Nicole

The professional in demand for VERA projects that need an engineer

Age 42
Location The Hague, NL
Job Technical Director
Work Place Digital Heritage Netherlands (DEN)
Expertise App Development

Tools

Sharing Email, Slack, Gsuite
Collab Jira, Testflight, Github
Other Website

Skills

Research ●●●○
 Analysis ●●●○
 Technical Tools ●●●○
 Social Media ●●●○

“I’m the intermediary that links the worlds of researchers and citizens”

Background

Working for DEN, a cultural and digital transformation organization, Nicole knows most of the experts in the field of digital humanities. She works in an agile way, so **she needs constant feedback from people to deliver the tools they need**. When working on projects, **she still deals with funding issues** and logistics, which often lead to many projects failing.

Scenario

Nicole **signed up for VERA a few months ago** when she heard about it at a conference. Because of app development expertise listed in her profile, **Nicole was matched to a VERA project**, created by a team at a humanities laboratory in Paris. The project is working to develop an easy-to-use web crawler which helps citizens curate and categorize websites of interest, and allows them to browse the resulting network in a visual way. **She messages with the project creator and after a few days, she is officially invited to the project** and added to the team. Along with Nicole, there's a Natural Language Processing engineer, research designer and a PhD student. **Nicole's role will be to help with project management and to coordinate the development of the app**.

The team is still missing some key roles, especially a communications officer to handle outreach. **Nicole looks for a journalist** and sends an invitation to a few. After talking with some journalists, **she finally selects one and adds her to the project**. To test the web crawler Nicole organizes an event at Leiden University. She needs to involve 4 students and **gets in touch with a university professor on VERA that helps her with recruitment**.

She also wants to find a data scientist to help with the data visualization side of the application, so **she posts on the “looking for” bulletin board in the VERA hub**, specifying the activity and time commitment requested. Nicole gets an email from a data scientist and is able to book her for next month. She adds the data scientist to her roadmap in VERA that syncs to Jira.

Thanks to the joint effort of the whole team, they manage to publish a prototype of their new web crawler and data visualization app. **Nicole is able to quickly find some users to check it out in the VERA hub**. Nicole has slowly built up a base of testers, which she tags in her network on VERA.

After the first testing of the prototype, the team starts focusing on finding funding to keep working on the project. The ability to **search the VERA hub for open calls** in citizen science app development, with visible budget availability makes the funding process more transparent and smoother. The team finds a suitable call to apply to and plans the next weeks' activities to prepare for the submission.

Goals

- Focus on physical outcomes like events for engagement
- Create tools that use crowdsourced data
- **Get iterative feedback** to speed up work
- Make sure citizens' needs are a priority from the start of a project
- Represent citizens when collaborating with researchers

Needs

- Improved coordination, especially with **getting citizen input and end-user feedback**
- Collaborative tools to simultaneously work together on documents
- Interdisciplinary teams to enable co-creation
- **Researchers for supervision on data analysis**
- More transparency between research and the public to minimize administrative issues

Challenges

- Feels rushed when working with researchers' busy schedules
- Major logistical issues on projects: **lack of sustainable funding, personnel is siphoned for external projects, data cleaning takes time**
- Has trouble convincing public on the importance of issues
- Cloud storage is always full from large files

Corbin

The journalist that needs scientific support and that is also willing to progress with his career

Age 31
 Location Paris, France
 Job Journalist
 Work Place Crim'HALT
 Expertise Data Analysis

Tools

Sharing Telegram & Gsuite
 Collab Excel & DataWrapper
 Other Visme

Skills

Research
 Analysis
 Technical Tools
 Social Media

“As a journalist, I need the complimentary work of researchers to tell the full story”

Background

When he started his career, Corbin didn't realize how much time he would spend in Excel! Very often for his work, he needs scientific research data in the domain of criminology and sociology: he tries to read a lot of research himself to fill in knowledge gaps. Sometimes that's not enough, so **he would like to get involved in a scientific community related to criminology, to find the scientific support he needs**, keep up-to-date and see **how his work can affect public opinion**.

Scenario

Corbin is now in the middle of a business-fraud analysis **project with 2 researchers on VERA**. The scope of the project is to **identify financial anomalies in the corporate sector** and eventually publish a series of articles to inform the public about how they can take legal action against business fraud.

One of the researchers didn't have too much experience with the types of business fraud the project deals with, so they created a **running shared glossary to define key terminology** used for the topic.

Since they are working with sensitive data, **the team appreciates the privacy settings** and knowing how data is used. They feel comfortable uploading information from their sources.

Since Corbin strives for close collaborations, he likes that there's always a Google Meet link in the project dashboard so he can quickly chat with collaborators when necessary. Another feature Corbin uses all the time is the **project diary**, which lets him quickly upload interesting photos from his phone and share with the team on the project dashboard wall. **He uses the diary to write notes on the progress of the project** and store drafts of infographics. He also starts to write an article about the project.

The updates in the project diary can also be **posted on the VERA hub to discuss it with the VERA community** and get feedback.

The **tutorials on VERA** have also improved his research skills; the one about Github integration inspired him to start using it for his data analysis results.

One of the researchers on the team endorsed Corbin for his Excel and data analysis skills and **referred him to another project proposal on VERA**. Combined with the feedback from other projects on his profile, Corbin now has an even stronger CV to get more collaborations and enrich his professional career.

Goals

- Inform the public on important issues and prepare their opinion on laws
- Learn more from research communities by engaging with them
- **Advance his career via collaborations**
- Have meaningful, on-going professional collaborations that give him a more complete picture of a topic
- **Work more with researchers because of the clarity and quality they bring to projects**

Needs

- Awareness of researchers' work and to collaborate closely with them to provide a more engaging story
- **To create a shared language with collaborators** at the beginning of the project
- **Flexible data privacy options and encryption** when communicating with collaborators

Challenges

- **Can feel restricted by researchers' rigid academic attitude**
- Extra tools for project management overcomplicate things
- A literal language barrier gets in the way of collaboration at times, requiring a translator

Petra

The passionate campaigner looking to find likeminded citizen scholars

Age 60
 Location Erfurt, Germany
 Job Salesperson
 Work Place Allianz Erfurt
 Expertise Law

Tools

Sharing Email & WhatsApp
 Collab Word
 Other Facebook

Skills

Research
 Analysis
 Technical Tools
 Social Media

“I work on these projects out of curiosity for issues that affect me”

Background

Petra is getting close to retirement, but she's more **active than ever in her local community**. She's become a leader on preservation of cultural heritage and historic places related to the German Democratic Republic (GDR) in her city.

Scenario

Petra is passionate about GDR history, and she is **looking for projects about the GDR's history** as witnessed in other parts of Germany. By chance, **she sees an ad for VERA** in the digital history newsletter she receives and signs up. **VERA suggests projects where German language knowledge is requested** and **she joins a project** working to map and transcribe a network of letters written between Germans in the GDR and those living in West Germany during the 80s, by tracking the senders and the receivers. There's a project manager, a historian and 2 other "citizen scholars" on the project, Petra will be responsible for transcribing, checking the work of the other citizen scholars and, because of her law expertise, help with the cultural preservation proposal that they will send to city hall at the end of the project.

Petra finds VERA useful because **she knows exactly what she needs to do; the roles are clearly defined** but it still feels like a democratic process. Her **activities on the project workspace were kindly set up by the coordinator**. The team members are also aware that Petra can only work during the mornings, something she specified when she registered on VERA.

While out for a walk, Petra gets a message on WhatsApp that a new document to be transcribed is in her project workspace. It actually is easier to work directly in the platform instead of downloading an attachment, making edits and comments and sending it back. Throughout the week, she works on the document and texts the coordinator when it's ready.

When she has trouble, Petra doesn't usually ask a researcher, but prefers to **mention one of her peers in the document or send them a message inside VERA**, which is faster than email.

By searching for related projects in the area on VERA, **Petra was able to connect with some like-minded users and organize an in-person workshop**, which was fun and brought her a lot of satisfaction.

She posted some pictures on her VERA blog. A week later, a journalist from another project contacted her for an interview. How exciting!

Goals

- **Create change through laws or events that unite people around a cause**
- **Put community and organizational needs before personal goals**
- Gain a new perspective from the collaborative experience and build enriching relationships
- Provide searchable data for researchers
- Engage with an open, democratic community to deepen knowledge

Needs

- **Digital and technical expertise**: help with a website for recruiting and social media for organizing events
- Flexible work commitments and simple, **asynchronous tools so that she can work independently and at her own pace**
- **Feedback for encouragement and to feel more satisfied with work**
- **Training and supervision** when in difficulty during a project
- To have a common goal, build trust and **see real world results**

Challenges

- Researchers use highly technical language and findings don't seem generalizable
- Doesn't like using social media, but it's an essential element of her working group
- **Wants to minimize time on the computer**
- No feedback due to volunteer nature of work
- Different levels of public administration don't communicate with each other, which limits and slows down work

